

Non Profit Marketing – (A Theoretical Approach)

Dr. T. Vijayalakshmi, Ms. S. Rubikaa & Ms. P. Sanjana

Assistant Professor / MBA

KSR College of Engineering (Autonomous), Tiruchengode

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Abstract

A non-profit organization is committed to furthering a particular social cause or pushing for a shared point of view. In economic terms, it is an organization that uses its surplus of the resources to besides achieve its ultimate objective, first than distributing its income to the organization’s shareholders, members or leaders. Nonprofits are tax-exempt or kind, meaning they do not pay income tax on the money that they receive for their organization. They can operate in a divine, research, scientific, or educational settings.

The key aspects of nonprofits are accountability, honesty, trustworthiness, and openness to every person who has invested time, money, and faith into the organization. Nonprofit organizations are accountable to the funders, donors, program recipients, volunteers and the public community. Public confidence is a part of the amount of money that a nonprofit organization can raise. The more nonprofits centre on their mission, the more public faith they will have, and as a result, more money for the organization.

Introduction

A (also known as an NPO) non-profit organization is an organization that uses its funding to pursue a specific direction, such as a charitable cause, rather than pursuing profits for its benefit as a for-profit business does. Some strength did not believe that spending in marketing strategies is essential for non-profits, but it is quite beneficial for an NPO to efficiently market itself. Non-profits use marketing tactics to assist with funding, growth and prosperity. Without these items, the overall mission of the NPO is diminished. Here’s how else non-profit marketing can help.

Non-profit Marketing Raises Awareness

Your non-profit organization is a brand. Therefore you need to raise information just like any other company or business. Marketing increases awareness of your brand and brand awareness spreads the message about your organization and your overall cause.

Non-profit marketing raises funds.

Non-profit marketing and non-profit fundraising go hand-in-hand. The more people that know about your organisation, the more potential funding you can bring in.

Non-profit Marketing Drives Donor Memberships and Recurring Donations

Many non-profit organizations offer donation memberships and monthly giving plans, like this one from Charity: Water. These programs are worthy because your organization doesn't have to fundraise so actively and so regularly, and they can help you raise more money — the average monthly online donation is \$52 (\$624 per year) compared to the normal one-time gift of \$128.

Marketing your non-profit gets your cause in front of fresh eyes and informs your donors about how they can consistently contribute.

Non-profit Marketing Recruits Volunteers

Non-profit marketing isn't just for funding — it also drives manpower (and woman-power!) to your organization. Despite industry or size, all nonprofits benefit from volunteers, and marketing your organization can help bring in new hands.

Moreover, missionaries are twice as likely to donate as non-volunteers.

Non-profit marketing promotes your services.

Funding, Awareness and volunteers are integral to your non-profit, but what about the purpose of your organization? What about the animals, people, or cause you're helping? Marketing can help with that, too.

The more characters who know about your non-profit organization, the more people you can help.

These are just a handful of ideas you should invest in marketing (particularly inbound marketing!) for your non-profit. Now, let's discuss how to build a non-profit marketing plan so you can start bringing in new funds, volunteers, and constituents.

Create a non Profit marketing plan

Define Your Marketing Goals

Your non-profit marketing plan exists to convert your organization's mission and big-picture objectives into necessary, actionable aims.

For example, let's say one of your purposes was to protect the welfare of animals in your community (like one of my favourite local rescues, I'd ask you to brainstorm three to five marketing ideas to further that objective.

Some ways you could use Marketing to drive that Objective include

Create and issue content that teaches your community on the status of animal welfare.

Post on social media about your organization and the pets you have for permission.

Send a weekly email newsletter sharing your content, adoptable animals, and missionary needs.

Host a regular event with educative resources, foster training, and adoption opportunities.

Understand Your Audience(s)

Non-profit marketing is separate from other types of marketing because your organization is likely targeting multiple groups: volunteers, constituents, donors and customers.

It's imperative to define and understand each of this public (a.k.a. user personas) because your marketing will vary based on who you're talking to. (We'll get into key messaging next.)

For model, following our animal shelter example from above, an email targeting donors will have different messaging than an email calling for volunteers.

One easy way to organize your diverse audiences is by using a CRM to segment the separate clubs. By separating contacts with tags and lists, you can simply send marketing messages to the appropriate groups.

Craft Your KeyWords

Keywords encompass the information you want your audiences to learn, hear, and share about your non-profit organization. Crafting these before you use your marketing is important for a few reasons:

Keywords keep your organization joined. No matter who’s doing the selling, you can be confident the same thing is being said and developed.

Key messages simplify your marketing. With these organised ahead of time, you already know what you’re going to say in your marketing messaging.

Key messages help organize your diverse audiences (as we talked about above). As a non-profit organization, you’re likely talking to constituents, volunteers, donors, and your community ... more personas than a typical for-profit business. Developing keywords for each of your audiences inform your team and your marketing to make sure you’re targeting the right collections.

Continuing with our animal shelter model, here’s a look at how you can craft a key message for different viewers.

Keyword: We protect the welfare of animals in our community through adoption, education and fostering, and animal advocacy.

For adoption constituents/ customers: By adopting or nursing, or by warning us of animals in need, you can help us protect the welfare of animals in our society.

For volunteers: We protect the welfare of animals through round-the-clock animal care and support.

For donors: You can help us protect the welfare of animals by donating to support advocacy, animal care and adoption promotion.

All of these key messages have the same purpose and suggestion, but they vary slightly depending on your audience. Together with your non-profit organization’s vision, mission, and goals, these messages will help effectively communicate and market your organization’s needs and purpose.

Plan, Choose and Create Your Marketing Strategies

Many marketers jump right to this step — creating and publishing various marketing tactics. Marketing encompasses much more than a blog post, advertisement, or event. To execute successfully, you must complete all the steps before this.

Now that you’ve established your aims (what you want), your key messages (what you’re going to say), and your readers (who you’re going to say it to), you can determine your marketing tactics (how you’re going to say it).

Marketing tactics refer to channels like events, email marketing, social media, and more. We’ve dedicated an entire segment to these marketing tactics — read about them in detail below.

Regardless of which tactic you choose, be sure to carry thorough preparation before and as you perform on it. Here are some questions to ask yourself as you make:

What will you do with this selling tactic?

When will these marketing activities take place?

Why is this tactic important?

Who will be effective for these activities?

How much do we think to spend?

How does this tie to our organization’s marketing goals?

The tactical plan is an integral part of your overall nonprofit marketing plan. How you approach your marketing policies and how they affect your organization is just as important as how you execute on them.

Before you hit the earth running on any of these policies, be sure your team has a regular game plan and a full understanding of it.

Marketing Strategies for Non-profit Organisations

Non-profit Email Marketing

You might be using email sporadically to call for missionaries or establish an online benefaction, but that's not enough. Email marketing is a highly effective marketing source, particularly for non-profit organizations. Why? It's personal and powerful.

Non-profit Event Marketing

Event marketing is one of the most efficient (and enjoyable!) ways to grow awareness of your organization, connect with raise funds, your community and garner support for your cause.

Non-profit Video Marketing

Whether they're consuming content for school, work, or fun, people prefer video content. As a non-profit organization, video marketing is a sure-fire way to garner interest and support from all of your audiences.

Non-profit Social Media Marketing

Social media is a highly attractive marketing strategy among nonprofits. Not only is it free, but it presents an avenue for organizations to show their brand characters and engage with their followers and supporters.

Non-profit Website

Every non-profit organization should have a website. A website works as a digital house base for your organization and includes critical information — what you stand for and how visitors can compete and help.

Non-profit Public Speaking

It's said that people buy into other people, not stocks. The same can be said about non-profit organizations. If customers believe in the people behind your organization, they're likely to buy in your cause and donate money or time.

Non-profit Content Marketing

Content marketing and blogging are valuable marketing assets for any non-profit organization. Findings:

Non-profit managers indicated that the most important marketing enterprises are promotional. The value of market research and strategic marketing was acknowledged only by a small proportion of non-profits, supporting Andreasen and Kotler's (2003) assertion that non-profit organizations have an "organization-centered" mindset. Only one-fifth of marketing staff are trained in marketing. Non-profit organizations did not differ in their use of marketing and marketing operations, suggesting that the relationship of market pressures may be more influential than the differences in operating environments.

Conclusions, Limitations and Future Work

The work of non-profit organizations is essential to maintain much-needed services typically not provided by the for-profit sector or the government. Given the processed market demands non-profit organizations are challenging and given that marketing as one of many operational market areas was approved by non-profit organizations some decades ago, the two core hypotheses of the quick study were that (1) non-profit organizations of the 21st century have managed to make the transition from an organization-centred marketing philosophy to a consumer-cantered or market-oriented philosophy and that (2) the increased use of marketing has led to a professionalization of the shopping workforce in non-profit organizations.

Many non-profit organizations still demonstrate a distinct lack of understanding of what the principles of marketing are and mostly focus their efforts on sales and promotional enterprises. Only a small proportion of staff members of the non-profit organizations who work in marketing are trained in marketing — suggesting that the increased market pressures faced by non-profit organizations in all countries weigh stronger than national differences in rules and regulations affecting to non-profit organizations.

As a consequence, non-profit organizations could have been slower in accepting the benefits of marketing to achieve their mission and adopting marketing strategies and techniques.

It would also be very exciting to try to map changes in the non-profit marketing mindset and professionalization over a longer period using a true longitudinal survey design. Finally, barriers to the acceptance of marketing practices, especially reasons why many non-profit managers believe that market research is unimportant or too difficult, would form an interesting qualitative follow-up investigation to the present study.

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